

Supplementary Document: “Cases of Similarity and Partial Similarity”

Using common correlation may over- or underestimate the actual connectivity between a seed and a target regions. The true connectivity might be discovered using partial correlations which correct for influences of other regions (here termed “volumes of no interest”). Constructing such cases is simple (see Pseudocode 1) and might play an important role in connectivity analysis of neuroimaging data as scenarios like an strong movement artifact (Case 3 in Supplementary Figure 1) are quite probable.

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x1=0:0.01:π*4;  
x2= x1*1.5;  
x3= x1*2.3;  
  
v=cos(x1);  
Case 1: no correlation between S and T  
s=cos(x2);  
t=cos(x3)+v;  
Case 2: correlation between S and T  
s=cos(x2);  
t=cos(x2)*0.7;  
Case 3: correlation between S and T induced by V  
s=cos(x2)+v;  
t=cos(x3)+v;  
Case 4: hidden communication between S and T: V pushes S but inhibits T  
s=cos(x2)+v;  
t=cos(x2)-v;
```

Pseudocode P1. Code used to construct the 4 sample cases for correlation and partial correlations.

Supplementary Figure S1. Simulated cases where common correlation and partial correlations show the same (Case 1 and 2) and divergent results (Case 3 and 4). Case 1 shows neither correlations nor partial correlations between seed (S) and target (T). The target is nevertheless influence by the Volume of No Interest (V). In Case 2, seed and target are correlated but though V has no influence on neither, correlation as well as partial correlation are equally high. In Case 3 (“induced correlation”) the interaction between the seed and target is overestimated as they are not interacting but are both influenced by V. While common correlation shows a strong connectivity ($c=0.5$), the influence of V is corrected for in the partial correlation which therefore becomes zero. This case is likely when there is a strong movement artifact in the whole measured volume or when a third region influences both, seed and target. Another example would be trivial correlations of the whole network, i.e. where all hubs of a network react simultaneously in the same way. Case 4 (“hidden correlation”) gives an example of underestimated connectivity where the relation between seed and target is overwritten by an excitatory influence of V on the seed but an inhibitory influence on the target. Also this connectivity can be discovered by partial correlation but not using common correlation.